

ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE AMONGST 0-3 YEAR-OLD CHILDREN FOLLOWED WITH A DIAGNOSIS OF FOOD ALLERGY

BESİN ALERJİSİ TANISIYLA İZLENEN 0-3 YAŞ ÇOCUKLARIN YAŞAM KALİTESİNİN BELİRLENMESİ

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Food allergy can adversely affect children's quality of life. This descriptive study was conducted with the aim of determining the quality of life of children aged 0-3 who were diagnosed with food allergy.

Methods: A total of 105 parents with children aged 0-3 and diagnosed with food allergy participated in the study. The data were collected using a 'Descriptive Information Form' and the 'The Food Allergy Quality of Life Questionnaire-Parent Form (FAQLQ-PF)'. Number, percentage, mean, and standard deviation values, as well as the Kruskal-Wallis test and Mann-Whitney U test, were used for data analysis.

Results: Among the participating parents, 76.2% were mothers, and 23.8% were fathers. The mean age of the children was 21.82±8.64 months, with 53.3% being male. 73.3% of the children were diagnosed with atopic dermatitis. The average score of the FAQLQ-PF was 2.40±0.73, indicating a moderate level of quality of life of children. There was a statistically significant difference in FAQLQ-PF scores based on the child's age and diagnosis (p<0.05).

Conclusions: According to mothers, the quality of life related to food allergy for children aged 0-3 years is at a moderate level in this study. It was observed that as the child's age increases, there is a decrease in the quality of life. Therefore, it is recommended to regularly assess the quality of life of children with food allergies.

Keywords: Child, Food Allergy, Quality of Life, Parents

ÖZET

Amaç: Bu çalışma besin alerjisi tanısıyla izlenen 0-3 yaş aralığındaki çocukların yaşam kalitesinin belirlenmesi amacıyla tanımlayıcı tipte yapılmıştır.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Araştırmaya besin alerjisi tanısı almış 0-3 yaş çocuğu olan 105 ebeveyn alınmıştır. Araştırma verilerinin toplanmasında "Tanımlayıcı Bilgi Formu", "Besin Alerjisi Hayat Kalitesi Anketi Ebeveyn Formu" kullanılmıştır. Verilerin analizinde sayı, yüzdelik, ortalama ve standart sapma değerleri, Kruskal-Wallis testi, Mann-Whitney U testi kullanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Çalışmaya katılan ebeveynlerin %76,2'si anne, %23,8'i babadır. Çocukların yaş ortalaması 21.82±8.64 ay olup %53,3'ü erkektir. Çocukların %73,3'ü atopik dermatit tanısıyla izlenmektedir. Çocukların Besin Alerjisi Hayat Kalitesi Anketi puan ortalaması 2,40±0,73 olup yaşam kaliteleri orta düzeydedir. Çocuğun yaşı ve tanısı ile Hayat Kalitesi Anketi puanları arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı fark vardır (p<0,05).

Sonuç: Çalışmada besin alerjisi ile izlenen 0-3 yaş grubu çocukların annelerine göre besin alerjisi yaşam kalitesi düzeyi orta düzeydedir. Çocuğun yaşı arttıkça yaşam kalitesinde düşmeler olduğu belirlenmiştir. Bu nedenle besin alerjisi olan çocukların yaşam kalitelerinin düzenli olarak değerlendirilmesi önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Aile, Besin Alerjisi, Çocuk, Yaşam Kalitesi.

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INTRODUCTION

Allergy, a hypersensitivity reaction primarily mediated by IgE and cell-mediated mechanisms, has seen a rising prevalence in conditions such as allergic rhinitis, asthma, atopic dermatitis, conjunctivitis, and food allergies in recent years (Sayar, 2020). Foods can elicit either immunologic or non-immunologic reactions in children. When an immunologic reaction occurs against foods, it results in the development of food allergies, while non-immunologic responses can lead to development of children's food intolerances (Manuyakorn & Tanpowpong, 2019). Food allergies are highlighted as significant public health issues that can adversely affect child health as a result of severe allergic reactions, often occurring in children under the age of 2 (Sicherer & Sampson, 2014), and arising from genetic and environmental factors (Gupta et al., 2018).

Food allergies can be classified as IgE-mediated, non-IgE-mediated, or of a mixed type (Manuyakorn & Tanpowpong, 2019). The estimated prevalence of food allergies in children is around 7.6-10% (Gupta et al., 2018; Licari et al., 2019; Sicherer & Sampson, 2014). In studies conducted in Türkiye, it has been reported that the most common allergenic foods for children under 2 are egg white, sesame, nuts, and cow's milk (Kahveci, Koken, Şahiner, Soyer, & Şekerel, 2020), and that the most common ones in children over 2 are cow's milk, peanuts, seeds, egg whites as well as tree nuts (Akarsu et al., 2021). Food allergy can lead to physical issues in children such as urticaria, angioedema, gastroenteritis, atopic dermatitis, contact dermatitis, and sometimes life-threatening anaphylactic reactions (Manuyakorn & Tanpowpong, 2019). On the other hand, food allergy can lead to a decrease in the intake of micronutrients such as vitamin D, zinc, and iron, causing growth retardation. Avoidance of three or more foods in children may lead to impaired growth measurements, especially a reported tendency for short stature relative to age in children having food allergies (Meyer, 2018).

Food allergy can also have psychosocial effects on children. The ones with food allergies might face exclusion, bullying in schools or social environments due to dietary restrictions (Walkner, Warren, & Gupta, 2015). On the other hand, due to the need for continuous avoidance of allergenic substances and coping with the challenges posed by food allergies alongside the changes brought about by normal developmental processes, children may experience an increased level of anxiety (Audrey DunnGalvin, Dubois, Flokstra-de Blok, & JO'B, 2015; Walkner et al., 2015). Children's quality of life is negatively affected due to both physical and psychosocial problems (Licari et al., 2019; Shaker, Schwartz, & Ferguson, 2017).

Quality of life can be influenced by factors including child's age, perceived severity of food allergy, in addition to the history of reactions (Walkner et al., 2015). Children diagnosed with food allergies typically do not have a specific treatment method other than avoidance of the allergen. However, licensed and potential treatment methods such as oral immunotherapy, cytokines, gene therapy, Anti-IgE, and probiotics can be utilized (Licari et al., 2019). A significant improvement has been reported in children's quality of life, particularly in the ones' treated with oral immunotherapy (Blumchen et al., 2019).

Food allergy can adversely impact children's health in various ways, leading to a negative impact on their quality of life. At this point, monitoring life quality of children undergoing treatment against food allergies is crucial.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design and setting

The descriptive type research was conducted between December 2022 and June 2023.

The following questions were investigated in the research:

Question 1: What is the quality of life of children monitored with food allergies?

Question 2: What are the factors influencing the quality of life of children monitored with food allergies?

Study Population/ Sample

Parents of 0-3 year old children who applied to the outpatient clinic between December 2022 and June 2023 and agreed to participate in the research were included in the sample. The research sample consisted of parents of 105 children aged 0-3 under follow-up in the paediatric allergy and immunology clinic of a university hospital.

Inclusion Criteria for the Study

- Parents of the children aged 0-3, diagnosed with food allergies,
- Those who do not have problems reading and understanding Turkish,
- Parents who agree to participate in the research.

Exclusion Criteria for the Study

- Parents of the children aged over 3.

Instruments

"Descriptive Information Form" and "The Food Allergy Quality of Life Questionnaire-Parent Form (FAQLQ-PF)" were used in the collection of research data.

Descriptive Information Form: The Form was prepared by the researchers in accordance with the literature, includes 17 questions about characteristics such as the age and educational status of the parents, the age and gender of the child (LeBovidge, Strauch, Kalish, & Schneider, 2009; Şenol & BT, 2015).

The Food Allergy Quality of Life Questionnaire-Parent Form (FAQLQ-PF): This scale was developed by Dunn Galvin et al. (2008) with the aim of determining the quality of life of children with food allergies (A DunnGalvin, De BlokFlokstra, Burks, Dubois, & Hourihane, 2008). The Turkish validity and reliability of the scale were conducted by Yilmaz et al. (Yilmaz et al., 2018). The scale consists of 14 items for children under the age of 4, 26 items for children aged 4-6, and 30 items for those aged 7-12. Each age group has three subscales (emotional impact (items 2, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11), food anxiety (items 1, 4, 5), social and dietary limitations (items 3, 8, 12, 13, 14)). Subscale scores are calculated by summing the scores. The raw scores for each item are divided by the number of items. The summary score is calculated by summing the subscale scores and then dividing by 3. The scale score ranges from 0 to 6; lower scores indicate better quality of life. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the scale range between 0.88 and 0.95.¹⁵ In this study, the 0-3 age section of the form was used.

Data Collection

The data were collected at a university hospital's paediatric allergy and immunology clinic. After providing information about the research to parents attending for examination, data collection forms were administered in an empty room within the clinic. Parents were asked to fill out the form themselves, and in cases where the parent needed to attend to their child, researchers read the survey items and marked responses accordingly. Data collection took an average of 15 minutes.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows 22.0 Program. Number, percentage, mean, and standard deviation values were calculated, and the data analysis included the use of the Kruskal-Wallis test and Mann-Whitney U test.

Ethical considerations

Prior to commencing the research, written permission was obtained from Ethics Committee of the University (01.12.2022-2022/14-23) and the hospital. Participants were informed about the research and had the opportunity to ask questions before data collection began. Subsequently, written consent was obtained from the participants.

RESULTS

Of the participating parents, 76.2% are mothers, and 23.8% are fathers. The average age of the mothers is 29.36 ± 5.61 , and the average age of the fathers is 32.57 ± 5.97 . 89.5% of the participants live in urban areas (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive Characteristics of Parents (n=105)

Age	(Mean \pm SD)	(Min-Max)
Mother's age	29.36 \pm 5.61	19-41
Father's age	32.57 \pm 5.97	22-46
Descriptive Characteristics		
	n	%
Parents Participating in the Study		
Mother	80	76.2
Father	25	23.8
Family Type		
Nuclear Family	94	89.5
Extended Family	11	10.5
Income Status		
Income Less than Expenses	59	56.2
Equal Income and Expenses	46	43.8
Mother's Education Level		
Primary School	29	27.5
High School	43	41
University	33	31.5
Father's Education Level		
Primary School	15	14.3
High School	48	45.7
University	42	40
Mother's Employment Status		
Employed	22	21
Unemployed	83	79
Father's Employment Status		
Employed	105	100
Place of Residence		
City	94	89.5
District	7	6.7
Village	4	3.8

The average age of the children is 21.82 ± 8.64 months, and 53.3% are male. 73.3% of the children are being monitored with a diagnosis of atopic dermatitis. 43.8% of the children have started complementary feeding by the sixth month, and 41.9% have an allergy to milk. 87.6% of the children need to avoid 0-2 foods (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive Characteristics of Children (n=105)

Descriptive Characteristics	n	%
Age (months) (Mean ± SD) (Min-Max)	21.82±8.64	2-36
0-12 months	22	21
13-24 months	50	47.6
25-36 months	33	31.4
Gender		
Girl	49	46.7
Boy	56	53.3
Diagnosis		
Atopic Dermatitis	77	73.3
Food Protein-Induced Enteropathy	23	21.9
Other*	5	4.8
Age of Introduction to Complementary Foods (months) (Mean ± SD) (Min-Max)	5.32±1.07	4-8
4	33	31.4
5	15	14.3
6	46	43.8
7 and 8	11	10.5
Time elapsed since diagnosis (months) (Mean ± SD) (Min-Max)	6.34±3.69	1-18
0-6 months	68	64.8
7-12 months	33	31.4
13-18 months	4	3.8
Allergenic Foods**		
Milk	54	41.9
Egg	31	24
Strawberry	18	14
Potato	12	9.3
Rice Flour	5	3.9
Tomato	4	3.1
Other***	5	4
Treatment **		
Steroid	79	50.3
Antihistamine	59	37.6
Nasal spray	19	12.1
Number of foods the child needs to avoid		
0-2	92	87.5
3-6	11	10.5
7-10	1	1
10 or more	1	1

* Anaphylaxis (n=1), urticaria (n=2), bloody stool (n=1), allergic rhinitis (n=1)

** Multiple responses were received. Row percentages are given for the number of cases.

*** Walnut (n=1), wheat (n=1), sesame (n=2), meat (n=1)

The lower scores on the FAQLQ-PF indicate better quality of life. The average score on the FAQLQ-PF is 2.40±0.73, indicating a moderate level of quality of life. The food anxiety average score is 0.31±0.71, which is the best level, while the social and dietary limitation average score is 3.44±1.04, which is below average (Table 3).

Table 3. FAQLQ-PF* Scores (n=105)

Scale	Mean ± SD	Min-Max
FAQLQ-PF*	2.40±0.73	0.33-4.93
Emotional impact	3.43±1.00	0-5.67
Food anxiety	0.31±0.71	0-3.33
Social and dietary limitations	3.44±1.04	0-5.80

* The Food Allergy Quality of Life Questionnaire-Parent Form

It has been determined that parents have low concerns regarding food safety. Concerns about their own health and the health of their children are above moderate. The stress level of family members related to food allergies is above moderate. Food allergies impact the activities of parents more than the moderate level (Table 4).

Table 4. Parents' Concerns Regarding Food Allergies (n=105)

Item	Mean ± SD	Min-Max
Concerns of parents regarding food safety *		
The possibility of eating a food to which one is allergic	1.28±1.24	0-6
The possibility of exhibiting a severe allergic reaction to the food consumed.	1.47±1.16	0-6
The possibility of dying after consuming a food to which one is allergic	0.34±0.61	0-3
The possibility of receiving ineffective treatment after consuming a food to which one is allergic.	0.57±0.95	0-5
The parent's overall health **	2.99±0.56	2-5
The child's overall health **	2.93±0.59	2-5
The parent's concern about the child's physical health***	3.62±0.85	1-5
The parent's concern about the child's emotional health***	3.60±0.88	1-5
The stress level of family members due to food allergies ***		
Himself/herself.	3.72±0.75	2-5
The spouse	3.13±0.69	1-5
The family	2.80±0.62	1-5
The impact of food allergies on activities***		
Family activities	3.29±0.74	1-5
Activities with the child	3.32±0.77	1-5

*Parents rated their concerns on a 0-6 point scale. 0 = very unlikely, 6 = extremely likely/possible.

** Parents rated their overall health on a scale of 1 (excellent) to 7 (very poor).

*** Parents rated their concerns on a scale of 1 (none) to 5 (very much).

There is a statistically significant difference in FAQLQ-PF scores based on the child's age and diagnosis ($p < 0.05$) (Table 5).

Table 5. Factors influencing the quality of life scores of children

Characteristics	FAQLQ-PF			
	n	M±SD	Test	p
Gender				
Girl	49	2.37±0.80	Z= -.610**	.542
Boy	56	2.42±0.68		
Age (months)				
0-12 months	22	2.17±0.53	X ² =6.093*	.048
13-24 months	50	2.33±0.60		
25-36 months	33	2.64±0.95		
Diagnosis				
Atopic Dermatitis	77	2.25±0.66	X ² =8.110*	.017
Food Protein-Induced Enteropathy	23	2.80±0.81		
Other***	5	2.72±0.74		
Age of Introduction to Complementary Foods (months)				
4	33	2.32±0.54	X ² =5.995*	.050
5	15	2.38±0.82		
6	46	2.43±0.82		
7 and 8	11	2.48±0.80		
Time elapsed since diagnosis (months)				
0-6 months	68	2.62±0.70	X ² =.865*	.834
7-12 months	33	2.64±0.70		
13-18 months	4	2.69±1.06		

*Kruskal-Wallis test.

** Mann-Whitney U test.

*** Anaphylaxis (n=1), urticaria (n=2), bloody stool (n=1), allergic rhinitis (n=1)

DISCUSSION

Food allergy is a disease characterized by a low mortality rate, impacting the lives of children and families across various dimensions of health, particularly dominated by psychological symptoms. Avoiding allergenic foods can impact the quality of life for both the child and the family due to the fear of allergic reactions (Birdi, Cooke, & Knibb, 2016; Blumchen et al., 2019). Considering that the language and cognitive abilities of young children develop over time, the responsibility on caregivers increases, especially for caregivers of small children with food allergies. Therefore, evaluating the quality of life of children monitored for food allergies is important. Parental reports are used in studies related to the quality of life of young children monitored for food allergies (Reier-Nilsen et al., 2019; Thörnqvist et al., 2019). In this study, the quality of life of children aged 0-3 with food allergies was assessed, and parental reports were used in the evaluation.

In our study, the scores of the FAQLQ-PF were found to be at a moderate level. In many studies in the literature, it has been reported that the quality of life of children monitored for food allergies is worse according to parental observations (Epstein-Rigbi, Goldberg, Levy, Nachshon, & Elizur, 2020; Indinnimeo et al., 2013; Yilmaz et al., 2018). These studies seem to evaluate the quality of life for all children aged 0-18. Although many studies evaluate all age groups, it has been reported that the quality of life scores for children under 3 years old is better than for older children (Howe, Franxman, Teich, & Greenhawt, 2014; Muraro et al., 2022; Wassenberg et al., 2012). In Kılıç's study (2023), it was also found that the quality of life scale scores worsened with age (Kılıç, Kaya, Taşçı, Özsoy, & Kılıç, 2023). In our study, the moderate level of quality of life scale scores is thought to be associated with the greater dependence on the family regarding the dietary regimen of children aged 0-3.

In our study, it was also determined that there was a significant difference between the child's diagnosis and the mean score of the quality of life, and that the quality of life of children followed with the diagnosis of Food Protein-Induced Enteropathy was worse. Food Protein-Induced Enteropathy is a condition characterized by recurrent diarrhea, vomiting, hypotension, hypothermia, lethargy after the consumption of a food (Caubet, Cianferoni, Groetch, & Nowak-Węgrzyn, 2019). Therefore, it is thought that the quality of life of young children is affected more due to increased fluid loss. In our study, it was determined that the quality of life of children diagnosed with atopic dermatitis was close to average. Atopic dermatitis can cause itching and negatively affect social and psychological well-being (Lifschitz, 2015). Therefore, it is important to monitor the quality of life of children with different types of diagnoses. Different studies in the literature report that the quality of life of girls is worse (Rosser, Lloyd, Hu, Loke, & Tang, 2024; Wassenberg et al., 2012). Differently, no significant difference was found between gender and quality of life in our study.

While food allergies impact the quality of life for the entire family, mothers tend to experience higher levels of anxiety compared to other family members (Kılıç et al., 2023; Westwell-Roper et al., 2022). Mothers tend to take on the majority of the responsibility in managing a child's food allergy, which can lead to increased stress for the child in terms of health preservation and management (Abrams, Simons, Roos, Hurst, & Protudjer, 2020; Ozturk, Merter, & Sengul, 2023). In our study, the anxiety levels of mothers were determined to be at a moderate level. It is believed that the establishment of a food regimen and the management of the disease process by mothers in the first three years of life are associated with the moderate anxiety levels observed in mothers. We found that as the child's age increased, the quality of life gradually deteriorated. This finding suggests that as the child grows, factors such as food preferences, the likelihood of being in different environments, and a decrease in maternal control make the management of food allergies more challenging, increasing the negative impact on quality of life.

In our study, the most significant factor affecting the quality of life is social and dietary restrictions. Dietary restrictions limit the family's eating habits, intra-family relationships, and, at the same time, activities in the social environment. Studies in the literature (Golding et al., 2022; Graham, Caubet, & Eigenmann, 2020) also support our findings that food allergies impose limitations in social settings due to dietary restrictions. In their study, Wassenberg et al. found that emotional impact and dietary restrictions significantly affected the quality of life scores of children with food allergies (Wassenberg et al., 2012). This situation affects the family emotionally. In contrast to our study, Goodwin et al. (2017) stated that the stress of children and parents with food allergies is not different

from families with healthy children (Goodwin et al., 2017). However, generally, the findings of many studies support our study.

Since our study included children and families aged 0-3 years, food allergies emerged as a condition that affects the child's and the family's food preferences, dietary restrictions, and social life. The study results show similarities with the literature in many aspects. However, the unique aspect of this study is its focus on the first three years of age, providing an opportunity for a detailed examination of the effects of being followed for food allergies on the lives of families, especially mothers. It is recommended that future research be conducted on a larger sample, using a mixed research design to identify the difficulties mothers face in detail.

Limitations

This study was conducted in only one hospital and the study results are limited to this hospital. Additionally, only parents of children aged 0-3 were included in the study. Therefore, the research results cannot be generalized to older children.

CONCLUSION

According to mothers, the level of food allergy life quality in children aged 0-3 years monitored for food allergies in the study is moderate. As the child's age increases, declines in life quality have been observed. It has been determined that parents, especially mothers, experience stress due to the child's dietary restrictions and social life limitations, and this situation has a significant emotional impact. According to the study results, the effects of monitoring food allergies in separate age groups based on developmental characteristics rather than the general childhood period should be thoroughly investigated. Providing information to families about the difficulties of providing care to children with food allergies and the psychosocial effects that may develop over time is appropriate to develop a multidisciplinary approach for children with food allergies. It is important to inform parents not only about the medical aspects of childhood diseases but also about preventive measures that can be taken. Teaching family members to recognize allergy symptoms and intervene in emergencies, read food labels, prepare safe recipes that the child can consume, and create a proper and balanced nutrition plan can be effective in improving the quality of life of children.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Plan, design: Z.K.S., O.S.M., Ç.S.O.; **Material, methods and data collection:** Z.K.S., O.S.M.; **Data analysis and comments:** Z.K.S.; **Writing and corrections:** Z.K.S., O.S.M., Ç.S.O

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